

ETHICAL VIEWS ON TAX EVASION AMONG SWEDISH CEOs: A COMMENT

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Abstract

This article comments on the article written by Ulrica Nylén² that was based on a survey of Swedish CEOs. The author challenges some of Nylén's premises, most notably the concept of stakeholder interest and the duties that taxpayers owe to various groups.

Some Problems with Premises

Prof. Nylén has written a most informative and interesting article. I have no quarrel with the empirical portion of the study. What I challenge are the premises upon which she bases her argument. Philosophical problems arise in the very first paragraph, which states:

Ethical issues in business arise in the particular relationships between a corporation and its various stakeholders. One important stakeholder group is

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² Ulrica Nylén, *Ethical Views on Tax Evasion among Swedish CEOs*, JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY, Vol. 1, No. 3 (Summer 1998). This article also appeared in Robert W. McGee, editor, THE ETHICS OF TAX EVASION (South Orange, NJ: The Dumont Institute for Public Policy Research, 1998), 260-282. All references are to the book.

"society at large", with whom the exchange process, among other things, consists of tax payments by the corporations to society. One ethical problem in this relationship might therefore be the negligence of corporations to pay prescribed taxes, i.e. engage in tax evasion and tax fiddling.³

The concept of stakeholder needs to be discussed. The stakeholder interest theory begins with the premise that corporations somehow owe a duty to individuals or groups other than the corporation's shareholders. The theory of the social responsibility of business begins with basically the same premise, so my criticisms of the stakeholder interest theory apply equally to the concept of the social responsibility of business.

Corporations are voluntary organizations that are formed for the purpose of making profits for their shareholders. The corporate board members owe a fiduciary duty to the shareholders not to dissipate shareholder wealth. It is not a corporation's duty to contribute to charity using corporate funds. If individual shareholders want to use their own resources to donate to charity, that is their business, but if the corporation's board members vote to donate corporate property to individuals or groups other than shareholders they violate their fiduciary duty to the shareholders.⁴ This argument has been made before,⁵ and it has also been

³ Nylén, at 260.

⁴ There are exceptions to this rule. Paul Newman's food products company is an example. Paul Newman, an American actor, established a food products company with the intent of donating the profits to charities. That is his announced intent and individuals who invest in shares of his company presumably are aware of this intent. If that is the case, the board does not violate any fiduciary duty by giving corporate assets to charity because they have the implicit approval of shareholders, who would not have invested in Newman's company otherwise.

⁵ Perhaps the classic article that takes this view is Milton Friedman, *The Social Responsibility of Business is to Increase its Profits*, which first appeared in The New York Times Magazine on September 13, 1970. This article has been reprinted many times, including in LEONARD J. BROOKS, PROFESSIONAL ETHICS

challenged.⁶ I do not want to rehash the arguments on both sides of this issue. Perhaps hundreds of articles and several books have already been written on this issue.

What I want to focus on is an overlooked philosophical aspect of this issue. Stakeholders are individuals or groups who have an interest in the outcome of the actions of others. In the case of a corporation, for instance, the neighborhood, city and state and the individuals who live therein are said to be stakeholders because a corporation that opens (or closes) a facility within their territory affects some individuals who live within these geographic locations. But it does not follow that the corporation in question has any duty to protect the interests of any of these groups. To make such an assertion would be to advocate a nonsequitur. Let's take an example.

Let's say that a supermarket opens across the street from a mom and pop grocery store.⁷ Mom and pop are likely to be driven out of business if the supermarket is allowed to open because mom and pop cannot compete. The supermarket can offer lower prices, a much larger variety of products and more convenient hours. It can also probably offer better parking facilities.

According to the stakeholder interest theory, mom and pop are stakeholders. However, it does not follow that the supermarket owes them any duty. Mom and pop are likely to be harmed by the competition from the supermarket. They may even lose their livelihood. But their rights are not violated because the supermarket does nothing to interfere with their right to enter into contract or to trade the property they have (food products) for the

FOR ACCOUNTANTS Minneapolis/St. Paul: West Publishing Company, 1995), 20-23.

⁶ One article that is critical of Friedman is by Thomas Mulligan, *A Critique of Milton Friedman's Essay "The Social Responsibility of Business is to Increase its Profits,"* which first appeared in the *Journal of Business Ethics*, vol. 5 (1986), 265-269, and is reprinted in BROOKS, *supra*, at 24-28.

⁷ I would like to thank Walter Block for providing me with this example. I have used it on several occasions to point out the difference between being harmed and having rights violated.

property they want (customer cash). Mom and pop have no right to prevent the supermarket from opening across the street and they have no right to demand that the supermarket do anything to protect them from being harmed.

The same holds true for so-called stakeholders who stand to be affected by the actions of some corporation. Individuals who live in a neighborhood where a corporation is thinking about pulling up stakes and moving, or closing down completely, may be adversely affected by the corporation's decision, but they have no right to prevent the corporation from doing what it wants with its own property. Allowing stakeholders other than the corporation's shareholders to force the corporation to do or not do something violates the owners' rights to property and/or contract.

Thus, my first challenge to Nylén regards something she said in the first sentence of the first paragraph, "Ethical issues in business arise in the particular relationships between a corporation and its various stakeholders." The only "ethical" issues that might arise between a corporation and its stakeholders is if the corporation's board dissipates shareholder wealth or if the corporation's managers defraud customers or violate someone's property or contract rights. Other than these instances, there really are no ethical issues to discuss, since the corporation owes no other duties to any other individual or group.

Another challenge to her premises arises in the second sentence, in which she states: "One important stakeholder group is "society at large", with whom the exchange process, among other things, consists of tax payments by the corporations to society." For one thing, corporations do not make tax payments to society; they make them to some government. Secondly, and perhaps more importantly from a philosophical point of view, "society" does not exist. Society neither eats nor breathes. "Society" is just a convenient collective term for a group of individuals who perhaps share some common interests and interactions and who live in more or less the same geographic location. Individuals or groups of individuals (like corporations) cannot owe a duty to someone who does not exist. No one can owe a duty to an inanimate object,

either. Duties can be owed only to individuals. If one has a duty not to burn down a building it is not because that individual owes a duty to the building but because a duty is owed to the owner of the building not to destroy property.

I think the point Nylén is trying to make is that some group of individuals (society) stands to benefit when corporations make tax payments to government and they stand to lose when these payments are not made. In a sense, she is correct, if this is what she meant. But it does not follow that corporations owe a duty to these individuals just because they stand to benefit or lose based on the corporation's decision to pay or not pay some tax. To draw such a conclusion would be a nonsequitur.

These individuals may be the recipients of some government money that must first be raised by taxing corporations. If the corporations do not pay the tax, the individuals who would otherwise receive benefits as a result of these tax payments stand to lose. The big question is "Do they lose something they are entitled to receive?" The answer is often no.

For example, if a corporation fails to pay all the property taxes it is legally required to pay, the local school system suffers. But it does not follow that the children who attend the government's schools have their rights violated because there is no right to force some individuals to pay for the education of other individuals.⁸ If a corporation fails to pay all the Social Security taxes it owes, some individuals on Social Security might be harmed, but it does not follow that the people who are on Social Security have their rights violated because they have no right to force some individuals or groups to pay for their pension benefits.

Both school taxes and Social Security taxes are special interest taxes. They do not benefit the majority. They benefit some special interest, school children in the case of school taxes and retired people in the case of Social Security taxes. Several

⁸ For more on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *Brown v. Board of Education: Forty Years of Asking the Wrong Question & the Case for Privatization of Education*, ST. LOUIS UNIVERSITY PUBLIC LAW REVIEW (1999), forthcoming.

authors have made the argument that there is no moral duty to pay special interest taxes.⁹ So if a corporation fails to pay a tax that benefits some special interest, it may be harming some individuals or groups but it is not violating any ethical duty because there is no ethical duty to pay a tax that benefits only special interests.

...the [Roman Catholic] bishops began turning over new ground by arguing that state taxation could never be justified for special interests. The placing of the interests of one group of people over another, in terms of taxation, was unjust. The state could not be permitted to tax particular groups within society to benefit other specific groups.¹⁰

Another underlying premise of Nylén's paper is the "fair share" argument. According to this argument, if some taxpayers do not pay their fair share, others have to pay more than their fair share. This argument has been made many times before, but it fails to hold up under analysis. Lehmkuhl, for example, takes the position that commutative justice is involved where the failure of

⁹ Rev. Martin T. Crowe, *The Moral Obligation of Paying Just Taxes*, The Catholic University of America Studies in Sacred Theology No. 84 (1944), 29 and several other places; Rev. JOHN F. CRONIN, *CATHOLIC SOCIAL PRINCIPLES* (Milwaukee: Bruce Publishing, 1950), especially at 463, as cited by Gregory M.A. Gronbacher in *Taxation: Catholic Social Thought and Classical Liberalism*, in Robert W. McGee, editor, *THE ETHICS OF TAX EVASION* (South Orange, NJ: The Dumont Institute for Public Policy Research, 1998), at 165, n. 16.

¹⁰ Gronbacher, *supra*, at 165. According to Islam there is no ethical duty to pay for something that protects special interests at the expense of the general public. For more on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *The Ethics of Tax Evasion in Islam*, in Robert W. McGee, editor, *THE ETHICS OF TAX EVASION* (South Orange, NJ: The Dumont Institute for Public Policy Research, 1998), at 215, which cites S.M. YUSUF, *ECONOMIC JUSTICE IN ISLAM* (Islamabad: The International Institute of Islamic Thought and the International Institute of Islamic Economics, 1995), 9-10.

one person to pay "just taxes" results in others having to pay more than their fair share.¹¹

There are several weaknesses with this line of reasoning. For example, it fails to answer the question of whether it is unethical for someone to evade an unjust tax where the result would be that others must pay more. Numerous authors over the centuries have concluded that there is no duty to pay an unjust tax, so it does not seem logical to conclude that this lack of ethical duty changes in cases where the unjust tax collector is forced to collect more from others just because one party's evasion reduces the total that the unjust tax collector would otherwise collect. It is the unjust tax collector who is acting unethically, not the taxpayer who merely wants to avoid having his property confiscated. It can never be unethical to try to keep property that rightfully belongs to you. The fact that more property must therefore be confiscated from others is another, separate issue.¹² But the morality of the issue revolves around the unjust tax collector, not the individuals who are merely trying to keep their property.

Another underlying premise of Nylén's argument is that there is somehow a moral duty to pay taxes if one receives, or is entitled to receive benefits. There are a number of problems with this premise as well. For example, what if government provides benefits but you did not ask for them? Is there any moral duty to pay Social Security taxes if you would prefer to invest in a private pension fund instead? Is there a moral duty to pay a tax that funds abortions if you think that abortions are immoral? Is there a moral duty to pay a tax that funds the arts if you don't go to operas and plays? It appears not.

¹¹ LEHMKUHL, *THEOLOGIA MORALIS* I, n. 981 (1902), as cited in CROWE, *supra*, at 76.

¹² For more on this and other related points, see Robert W. McGee, *Is Tax Evasion Unethical?* 42 *UNIVERSITY OF KANSAS LAW REVIEW* 411-435 (Winter 1994).

What if you actually do receive some benefit from the taxes you pay? Do you still have a moral duty to pay them? Nylén's underlying premise is that you do. I disagree.

The average taxpayer receives less in benefits than what he has to pay if for no other reason than deadweight loss. The cost of collection and administration results in the distribution of less than 100 percent of what is collected in the form of taxes. Let's say that the average taxpayer receives benefits equal to 60 percent of taxes paid.¹³ Does the fact that taxpayers are forced to pay \$100 for every \$60 in benefits mean that they are morally obligated to pay the \$100? I think not. Indeed, the fact that they are forced to pay anything is a strong indication that there is no moral obligation to pay anything. Where force is involved, there is no moral choice.

Concluding Comments

While the empirical portion of Nylén's article is quite good, she could have made the article even better by first examining some of the premises upon which it is based. The article is not weakened much by her overlooking these points, since the empirical results are not affected much by the overlooked premises. The stakeholder interest theory and the related social responsibility of business theory are so laden with philosophically indefensible premises that they should never be used as the basis of an argument. But since Nylén's article only tangentially deals with these fatally flawed theories, the main points of her article remain intact.

¹³ The actual percentage received depends on a number of factors. The 60 percent given in this example is merely that, an example.